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Evaluation of steam-treated giant bamboo for production of fermentable sugars

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Abstract

Giant bamboo plantations are currently being established in the Southern Africa region and can be considered as potential lignocellulosic feedstock for the production of second generation bioethanol. In this study, giant bamboo internodal material was subjected to sulphur dioxide (SO₂) impregnated steam pretreatment prior to enzymatic hydrolysis. The effect of temperature, residence time and acidity on the overall sugar recovery and byproduct formation was studied using response surface response technology according to a central composite experimental design (CCD) at a fixed SO₂ concentration of 2.5% (w/w liquid) after impregnation.

The results showed that pretreatment conditions with combined severity factor (CSF) values and enzyme dosages greater than 1.72 and 30 FPU/g WIS, respectively, were required to obtain an efficient glucan digestibility and a good overall glucose recovery. Up to 81.2% of the sugar in the raw material was recovered for a CSF of 2.25. However, considering overall sugar yield and byproducts concentration, the pretreated material obtained with a CSF of 1.62 can be considered as the most appropriate for SSF experiments using a xylose-utilizing yeast. At these conditions, it could be possible to obtain up to 247 L of ethanol per dry ton of giant bamboo considering hexose and pentose sugars fermentation. This amount could be increased up to 292 L of ethanol per dry ton of giant bamboo with the maximum sugar yield obtained (CSF=2.25) if the microorganism possesses robust fermentative characteristics as well as a high resistance to pretreatment by-products.

Keywords: Bamboo; SO₂-catalyzed steam pretreatment; Combined Severity Factor; Enzymatic Hydrolysis; Bioethanol

1. Introduction

The pressures of an increasing global population along with dwindling energy supplies and environmental concerns such as climate change have prompted the cultivation of bioenergy crops to supply an alternative renewable source of biofuels and chemicals to supply the increasing demand for liquid fuel. Perennial herbaceous grasses such as bamboo present an interesting option since they are characterized by rapid growth, reaching maturity within five years and heights up to 40 meters.^{1,2} Bamboo plantations presents other beneficial attributes which include limiting soil erosion in cropping systems, potential of bioremediation, improving water quality, protecting stream banks, having lower chemical and nutrient requirements and increasing the organic matter content of the soil.³⁻⁷

Bamboo is classified as perennial grasses and forms part of the subfamily Bambusoideae.⁸ A variety of bamboo species, especially giant bamboo (*Bambusa balcooa*), occur widely in tropical, subtropical and temperate regions and most notably in the Oriental regions including India, China, Korea and Japan.^{9,10} Bamboo biomass has been used for many commercial applications including the food, textile, construction, and pulp and paper industry.² Apart from being a commodity of extensive social and economic importance in Asia, the use of this natural resource is rapidly gaining ground throughout Africa and Latin America.^{11,12} Currently, giant bamboo plantations are being established in the Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) region to provide raw material for export as well as for the production of high-value paper-pulp and biofuels.^{2,9}

The beneficial properties of bamboo emphasize its potential as an emerging lignocellulosic feedstock for ethanol production. Ethanol process based on enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) has the potential to convert these carbohydrates into fermentable sugars with high yields. However, the recalcitrance of the lignocellulosic matrix to enzymatic and microbial degradation requires thermo-chemical pretreatment in order to increase cellulose

accessibility.¹³ Steam pretreatment (SP), especially with the addition of an acid catalyst such as sulphur dioxide (SO₂), dissolved in the moisture present in the biomass by saturation, is a proven method for the effective pretreatment of a variety of softwoods¹⁴, hardwoods¹⁵ and agricultural residues¹⁶. However, limited information is available on the application of SP to giant bamboo.^{8, 17-19}

In this study, the effect of two SP process parameters, namely time and temperature was investigated on sugar recovery, byproduct formation and cellulose digestibility of giant bamboo at a fixed level of SO₂-impregnation. A central composite design (CCD) was applied to identify pretreatment conditions that enhanced the overall yield of potentially fermentable sugars, while minimising the degree of byproducts formation. The severities of the different pretreatment conditions were compared using the combined severity factor (CSF), where the temperature, residence time and acidity of the pretreated material were combined into a single reaction parameter.

2. Material and Methods.

2.1. Raw Material

Bambusa balcooa (giant bamboo) that was on average 10 years of age was obtained from Paarl in the Western Province of South Africa. The internodal areas of the bamboo shaft were cut in 1 cm² blocks, dried at 40 °C and stored at room temperature. Before pretreatment, the material was rehydrated to 45-55% moisture by soaking the bamboo blocks in water. Subsequently, the wet material was milled and sieved using a 4 mm screen to isolate chips for steam pretreatment.

2.2. Steam pretreatment

Milled bamboo was impregnated with SO₂ by sealing the wet material (500 g dry matter content) for 30 min in plastic bags to which 16 g of SO₂ gas was added. Subsequently, the reopened bags were placed in a well-ventilated area to allow excess SO₂ gas to disperse.

The average SO₂ content of the material was calculated as 2.5% (w/w liquid) based on the difference in mass of the material before and after SO₂ exposure.

The impregnated material was introduced into a 10 L steam pretreatment reactor described elsewhere²⁰ and pretreated at temperatures and residence times as described in the text. After collection of the material from the discharge vessel, the slurry was filtered to recover the solid and liquid fractions. The solid fraction was thoroughly washed with distilled water and stored at 4 °C prior to analysis and enzymatic hydrolysis tests.

2.3. *Experimental Design*

The SP process in combination with SO₂ impregnation is generally used to enhance the digestibility of softwoods through selective removal of hemicellulose.¹⁴ A Central Composite Design (CCD) is a valuable statistical tool where a dependent variable can be optimized within the boundaries of specific independent variables. In the present study, the total sugar yield (Y, g/100 g oven dry raw material), considering glucose and xylose, from bamboo was evaluated by applying a CCD, changing the pre-treatment temperature (X1, °C) and time (X2, min) within a range specified in Table 1, at a constant catalyst loading of 2.5% SO₂ (w/w liquid). The range of temperature was selected based on preliminary experiments performed on tubular reactors (unpublished data). The catalyst concentration was fixed at 2.5% (w/w liquid) since several studies have proven that SO₂ levels above this value had no beneficial effects in terms of increased sugar yields.^{16, 21}

An experimental design was created using STATISTICA 9 (Statsoft Inc., Tulsa, USA) software package. Each independent variable was tested on two levels in a rotatable 2³ CCD with 4 centre points and 4 star points, where the star points allowed the model to predict non-linear responses. A total of 12 experiments were conducted in a random order. The response

surface as predicted by the CCD was simplified to a quadratic polynomial model of the following form:

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \cdot X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} \cdot X_i^2 + \sum_{i \leq j}^k \sum_j^k \beta_{ij} \cdot X_i \cdot X_j + \dots + e \quad (1)$$

where i is the linear coefficient, j the quadratic coefficient, β the regression coefficient, k the number of factors studied and optimized in the experiment and e the random error. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to investigate the main effects and the interaction of two factors. Factors with a confidence level of less than 95% ($p > 0.05$) were removed and expressed in terms of error. The accuracy of the model was further expressed by the coefficient of determination (R^2), which is an indication of the variance existing between the predicted and experimental values.

2.4. Enzymatic Hydrolysis

The digestibility of the solid material was evaluated using enzymatic hydrolysis (EH). The different solid fractions were washed with de-ionized water to remove all water-soluble solids and then vacuum filtered with Whatman® GF-A. The water insoluble solid (WIS) was enzymatically hydrolyzed to determine the effect of the different pretreatment conditions on the digestibility of the glucan. Enzymatic hydrolysis assays were performed in 24 ml glass tubes, each containing 10 ml of 0.05 M sodium citrate buffer (pH 4.8), 0.02% (w/v) sodium azide and a substrate loading of a 2% (dw/v). Hydrolysis was allowed to continue for 72 h in a shaking water bath adjusted to 50 °C. Two cellulose-hydrolyzing enzyme preparations, namely Spezyme CP (Genencor, Leiden, Netherlands) with an activity of 65 FPU/ml, and Novozym 188 (Novozymes A/S, Denmark) with a β -glucosidase activity of 590 IU/ml were

used in all experiments. Enzyme loadings for Spezyme CP of 15, 30 and 45 FPU/g dry material (equivalent to 32.3, 74.6 and 96.9 mg protein/g, respectively) were used, whereas β -glucosidase loadings from Novozym188 were 15, 30 and 45 IU/g dry material (equivalent to 2.6, 5.2 and 7.8 mg protein/g, respectively). Samples were withdrawn from the hydrolysis reactions after 72 hours for analysis of cellobiose, glucose and xylose.

2.5. Analytical Methods

Enzyme preparations were subjected to standardized tests to determine the protein content and activities of the main enzymes relevant to the conversion of lignocellulose, namely cellulase and cellobiase. Cellulase and β -glucosidase activities were measured according to methods described by Ghose (1987).²² The protein content was determined using a bicinohonic acid assay ([BCA]TM; BCA-Compat-Able Protein Assay kit, ref. 23229, Pierce, Rockford, IL) using bovine serum albumin as protein standard.

The composition of the extractives-free raw material and the solid fraction of steam-exploded bamboo were determined using the standard Laboratory Analytical Procedures for biomass analysis provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL, Colorado, USA).²³ The starch content of the raw material was determined using a starch hydrolysis kit from Megazyme (K-TSTA Lot no. 70302-2, Wicklow, Ireland).

The liquid fractions from the pretreated material were analyzed for their monomeric and oligomeric sugar content. The oligosaccharide concentration was defined as the difference in monomer sugar concentration before and after complete acid hydrolysis of oligosaccharide sugars. Concentrations of glucose, xylose and arabinose and by-products such as acetic acid, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and furfural in the liquid fraction were analyzed using an Aminex HPX-87H Ion Exclusion Column equipped with a Cation-H cartridge (Biorad, Johannesburg, RSA). Sugars were measured with a RI detector (Waters

2141, Microsep, Johannesburg, RSA), whereas by-products were analyzed with a UV detector set at 220 and 280 nm (Waters 2487, Microsep, Johannesburg, RSA). The column was operated at 65 °C with a mobile phase of 5 mM sulphuric acid and a flow rate of 0.6 ml/min. After completion of EH assays, cellobiose, glucose, xylose and arabinose concentrations in the supernatant were measured using the same HPLC method described above. Each sample was filtered through a 0.2 µm nylon membrane filter before HPLC analysis. All analytical determinations were performed at least in triplicate and average results are shown.

The similar retention times of xylose and galactose caused co-elution from the HPX-87H column operated under these conditions. However, complete analysis of the original raw material was performed by high performance anionic exchange chromatography on a Dionex Ultimate® 3000 system equipped with a CarboPac PA1 column (4x250 mm) operated at 25 °C with a mobile phase of 30 mM sodium hydroxide and a flow rate of 1ml/min. This analysis showed that the galactan content of the raw material (dry weight) was below 0.5% (w/dw), compared to the xylan content that was measured at 17% (w/dw). Therefore, the influence of galactose was ignored.

2.6. Calculations

The combined severity function (CSF) can be used to correlate the effects of temperature, the residence time and the acidity in the reaction media with the effectiveness of biomass pretreatment²⁴. The combined severity factor function is as follows:

$$\text{CSF} = \text{Log}R_0 - \text{pH} \quad (2)$$

where R_0 is the severity factor and the pH refers to the acidity generated in the reaction media (measured after pretreatment) by the addition of an acid catalyst and the release of organic acids from the raw material. R_0 is given by the following equation:

$$R_o = t \times \exp \left[\frac{(T - 100)}{14.75} \right] \quad (3)$$

The enzymatic hydrolysis yield (EH) was calculated as the hydrolysed glucan (HC) divided by the total glucan content in the WIS and expressed as percentage. The hydrolysed glucan was calculated considering the glucose and cellobiose content in the media, after applying weight adjustment for analyzed sugars. EH yield was calculated as follows:

$$EH (\%) = ([\text{glucose}] + 1.053 [\text{cellobiose}]) / 1.111 f [\text{biomass}] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where, [Glucose] and [Cellobiose] are the concentrations (g/l) of glucose and cellobiose in the supernatant, respectively; [Biomass] is the dry biomass concentration at the beginning of the hydrolysis (g/L); f is the glucan fraction in dry biomass (g/g); 1.053 and 1.111 are factors to determine equivalents of glucose from cellobiose and glucan respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Raw material composition

A summary of the chemical composition of the dry raw material is presented in Table 2. Bamboo consisted predominantly of glucan, xylan and acid insoluble lignin that added up to 78.5% on a dry weight basis. The inorganic content was relatively low at 2.4%. Therefore, up to 61.4% of the dry raw material consisted of glucan and hemicellulose that could be used for ethanol production. The hemicellulose component consisted primarily of xylan (16.7 %), small amounts of arabinan (3.1%) and a significant amount of acetyl groups (3.7%).

Generally the carbohydrate composition of the giant bamboo corresponded well with values reported in literature for different bamboo species.^{8,9,18,19,25} However, the chemical composition of the bamboo differed substantially from that known for herbaceous biomass. The acetyl group content of 3.7% was comparable to those reported for hardwoods²⁶, suggesting that a major part of these substituents could be released as acetic acid during the

pretreatment. The total lignin content of 31.7% was in line with the lignin ranges reported for softwoods (25-35%).²⁷

Pretreatment efficiency is highly dependent on the composition of the biomass. Based on the composition of giant bamboo presented herein, some responses to the pretreatment can be expected. For example, the low inorganic content of giant bamboo will have a low buffering effect on of the acid catalyst during the pretreatment. Regarding the hemicellulose fraction, the similarities in the content of xylose and acetyl groups between bamboo and hardwoods suggested that a similar degree of hemicellulose solubilization will occur during SP. However, the high lignin content could involve lower values of cellulose digestibility due to increased material recalcitrance and unproductive binding of hydrolytic enzymes.²⁶

3.2. Steam pretreatment

The influence of temperature, residence time and acidity of the pretreatment process on the chemical composition of the liquid and solid fractions of the bamboo was investigated. The effect of these parameters was also evaluated in terms of sugar solubilization during pretreatment and susceptibility of the WIS to EH. These two responses were used to assess the overall sugar yield, considering sugar solubilization during pretreatment and sugar released during EH.

3.2.1. Effect of steam pretreatment on composition of giant bamboo

The solids recovery (insoluble solids remaining after pretreatment divided by original oven-dried weight), combined severity factor (CSF) and the composition of the different fractions obtained after SE pretreatment conducted under different conditions are shown in Table 3. The CSF was calculated by combining the temperature and retention time with the acidity of the pretreatment mixture resulting from the acid catalyst and organic acids released during the pretreatment.²⁴ Solid recovery values from the different pretreatment conditions

varied between 63.2 and 89%. During pretreatment the solubilization of components such as extractives and hemicellulose led to enrichment of the glucose and acid insoluble lignin (AIL) content of the solid fraction, resulting in glucose values ranging from 51.3 to 65.5% and AIL ranging from 22.8 to 27.8%. The glucose solubilized in the liquid fraction varied between 1.4 and 2.5 g/100 g raw material, corresponding with 3 and 5.5% from the initial glucose content in the raw material, respectively. Only at the harshest conditions (CSF=2.25 and 2.26) glucose losses were observed, being less than 6%.

An increase in the severity of the pretreatment conditions resulted in a decrease in xylose content of the water insoluble solids (WIS) with the subsequent increase in xylose concentration in the liquid fraction. In fact, no xylose could be detected in the WIS from material pretreated at the most severe conditions of 210 °C for 9 minutes and 214 °C for 6 minutes (Table 3). The xylose content of the WIS at the central point of the CCD (200 °C for 6 minutes) was approximately 2.2%, which corresponded to 8.5% of the initial xylose content in the raw material. Under milder conditions, the xylose content in the WIS varied from 5.7% (190 °C for 9 minutes) to 11.1 % (190 °C for 3 minutes) corresponding to 24 and 50% of the initial xylose content in the raw material, respectively. The xylose solubilized in the liquid fraction varied from 4.8 to 12.8 g/100 g raw material corresponding with 25% to 68% of the initial xylose content in the raw material. The xylose recovery from both fractions decreased from 81 to 51% when the severity of pretreatment was increased.

Statistical analysis was used to determine whether different pretreatment conditions had a significant effect on the solubilization of the hemicellulose. This was necessary since the removal of hemicellulose is considered as an indicator of the effectiveness of pretreatment.²⁸ Analysis of variance where the yields of xylose recovery was considered as the response variables showed that differences in solubilization between pretreatment conditions were significant (P-value >0.05). The coefficient of determination of the model

was 0.73, which further indicated that the model was relatively suitable for representing the interaction between the selected variables. The polynomial equation for the xylose yield can be written as:

$$\text{Xylose yield} = 11.4 + 1.4T - 1.6T^2 + 1.2t - 2.2Tt \quad (5)$$

$$R \text{ squared} = 0.85; R \text{ adjusted} = 0.73$$

where T represents the temperature and t the residence time.

Equation (5) indicated that both temperature and time influenced the xylose solubilization during the pretreatment. Moreover, the negative sign of the temperature parameter and the interaction between temperature and time showed that the xylose yield in the prehydrolysate decreased from certain values of these parameters. This can be observed in the response contour for Equation 5 where the xylose yield in the prehydrolysate was plotted as a function of the temperature and residence time of pretreatment (Figure 1). When experiments were carried out for 6 minutes, an increase in temperature from 186 °C to 200 °C resulted in an increase in the xylose yield from 4.8 to 11.5 g/100 g of the raw material. The xylose content in the liquid decreased to 10.1 g/100 dry material upon a further increase in temperature to 214 °C, which was indicative of by-product formation.

Together with acetic acid, the respective degradation products of pentoses and hexoses, primarily furfural and HMF, are considered as the most abundant inhibitors from steam explosion for the downstream processing.²⁹ The yield of acetic acid, furfural and HMF, expressed as g/100 g raw material are represented in Figure 2 as function of the combined severity factor. An increase in the severity of the pretreatment conditions resulted in an increase in the yield of the degradation products, reaching the maximum values at a CSF value of 2.26, which corresponded to pretreatment conditions of 210 °C for 9 minutes. At these conditions, furfural and HMF reached maximum yields of 0.8 and 0.2 g/100 g dry

bamboo, respectively. Furthermore, the acetic acid yield increased up to 2.7 g/100 g of dry bamboo.

Acetic concentrations up to 6 g/l at an adjusted pH of 5.5 have been reported to increase the ethanol yield of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* whereas further increases in the acetic acid concentration resulted in decreased ethanol yields.³⁰ In our study, acetic acid concentrations greater than 6 g/l (corresponding with 1.5 g/100 g dry bamboo) were recorded when the CSF value was greater than 1.72 (Figure 2). Additionally, strains of *S. cerevisiae* have been shown to detoxify hydrolyzates with concentrations of furfural and HMF up to 1.2 and 0.3 g/l respectively.³¹ In our study the concentrations of furans were in excess of these acceptable maximum levels when pretreatment was conducted at a CSF higher than 1.95.

The prehydrolysate from the pretreatment, which consists mainly out of xylose, can be fermented to ethanol by microorganisms utilizing pentoses.³² In this study, the maximum xylose yields were obtained for CSF values of 1.45 (190 °C for 9 minutes) and 1.62 (central point of the CCD 200 °C for 6 minutes) where 12.3 and an average of 11.5 g xylose/100 g of dry bamboo were recovered in the liquid fraction, respectively (Table 3). Furthermore, the amounts of inhibitors produced under these conditions were less than 0.8, 0.2 and 3.6 g/l (corresponding to 0.3, 0.1 and 1.3 g/ 100 g raw material) for furfural, HMF and acetic acid respectively. These amounts have been found to be below the inhibitory level in both enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.^{30, 31, 33}

3.2.2. Enzymatic hydrolysis of steam-pretreated bamboo

The effect of different pretreatment conditions on cellulose digestibility was assessed through EH of the WIS fraction of the pretreated bamboo at a solid loading of 2% (dw/v) and an enzyme dosage of 15 FPU/g WIS. The enzymatic hydrolysis yield was expressed as a

percentage of glucan hydrolyzed in relation to potential glucan in each WIS fraction after 72 h (Table 3).

Steam pretreatment improved the glucan conversion of giant bamboo by EH with 15 FPU/g WIS. The glucan conversion of the material produced under different pretreatment conditions ranged from 6.9 to 62.7% of the theoretical glucan conversion potential (Table 3) and was much greater than the approximately 2% glucan conversion of untreated bamboo (data not shown). The correlation between pretreatment parameters (T , temperature and t , time) and the glucan digestibility (GD) for 15 FPU/g WIS was determined by ANOVA using the following equation:

$$GD = 43.9 + 20.5T + 10.7t - 6.3t^2 \quad (6)$$

$$R = 0.95; R_{adj} = 0.91$$

The effect of temperature and time of the SP on cellulose digestibility for an enzyme dosage of 15 FPU/g WIS was studied by standardized Pareto chart (Figure 3.A.1.) and response surface methodology (Figure 3.B.1.). The temperature and time exerted mainly a linear positive effect on the digestibility of glucan for the studied range, with temperature being more influential at a 95% confidence level (Figure 3.A.1.).

Higher enzyme loadings generally result in higher glucose yield up to certain level (saturation) that may differ depending on pretreatment conditions. Since the yields obtained with 15 FPU/g WIS were below 63%, enzyme loadings of 30 and 45 FPU/g WIS were used to study whether higher dosage will improve glucan conversion. To simplify interpretation of the data, the combined severity factor (CSF) was considered as an independent variable to evaluate the effect of SP conditions and enzyme dosage (E) on glucan digestibility. The CSF was chosen instead of the severity factor due to differences in the acidity of the pretreated

materials. The combined severity factor along with the enzyme dosage was statistically significant in the glucan digestibility (GD) according to the equation:

$$GD = 35.3 + 8E + 39.3CSF - 9.7CSF^2 + 6.5 E CSF \quad (7)$$

$$R = 0.90; R_{adj} = 0.88$$

As expected, the higher enzyme loadings provided greater values of glucan digestibility although this improvement depended on the conditions of pretreatment. From the standardized Pareto chart (Figure 3.A.2.) it can be inferred that the CSF exerted the greatest influence on the cellulose digestibility. Additionally, a response surface to estimate the enzymatic hydrolysis yield over the independent variables of CSF and enzyme concentration at 72 h (Figure 3.B.2.) showed that a greater increase of the enzymatic hydrolysis yield was obtained by increasing both CSF and enzyme loading for the studied range. A CSF of 1.95 was required to obtain materials with glucan digestibility of at least 80% for an enzyme loading of 45 FPU/g WIS (Table 3). The maximum EH observed (91.3%) was attained for the harshest conditions (CSF=2.26).

Xylan removal from the solid fraction is closely related to cellulose susceptibility during EH, as has been reported previously.²⁸ The improvement of glucan conversion with increasing the severity factor had an inverse correlation with the xylan removal. For example, the hydrolysis yield of the WIS obtained from the most severe conditions with a complete xylan removal (210 °C for 9 minutes, CSF=2.26) reached values of 91.3% at 45 FPU/g WIS (Table 3). By contrast, just 42% of hydrolysis yield was obtained under milder pretreatment conditions (190 °C for 9 minutes, CFS= 1.45, xylan removal by 70 %) at the same enzyme dosage. These values decreased to 10.2 and 13.2% for the WIS with the higher xylan content (about 10% dw).

The enhancement of the digestibility of bamboo by means of steam pretreatment has been reported in other studies. EH yields obtained in this study at CSF greater than 1.45 are better than those reported by Asada et al.³⁴ at harsher conditions and higher enzyme loading. Nonetheless, the yields attained in our work at the standard enzyme loading were in line with the low conversion reported for softwoods³⁵. These low values could be attributed to unproductive binding of the enzymes to the lignin which is high in giant bamboo. In fact, an EH yield of 84.3% with an enzyme loading of 20 FPU/g WIS has been reported for steam treated bamboo subjected to an additional delignification step.¹⁹

3.2.3. Overall sugar yield

An efficient pretreatment method should disrupt the lignocellulose structure to increase the accessibility of the enzymes, thereby enhancing the enzymatic hydrolysis yield. However, harsh conditions will result in sugar loss and production of inhibitors for downstream processing. Therefore in establishing optimum conditions it is important to measure the recovery of all sugars, including those solubilized during pretreatment.

The recovery of glucose monomers and oligomers after pretreatment, as well as the glucose released during enzymatic hydrolysis is represented in Figure 4A. The overall glucose yield varied from 6 g/100 g raw material under milder pretreatment conditions to 42.3 g/100 g raw material when bamboo was pretreated at 214 °C for 6 min (CSF=2.25). This maximum overall glucose yield was slightly greater than that obtained during pretreatment at 210 °C for 9 min (41.6 g /100 g dry giant bamboo), which provided the maximum enzymatic hydrolysis yield on a WIS basis (91.3%, Table 3). On average, a lower overall glucose yield of 29.9 g/100 g dry giant bamboo was obtained when using the conditions at the central point of the CCD (200 °C for 6 min), which corresponded to 65.4% of the maximum theoretical.

Since the xylose is the major component in the hemicellulose structure of bamboo, its recovery would make a significant contribution to the final ethanol yield, especially when an industrial pentose-fermenting microorganism is used for fermentation. The pretreatment conditions which provided the higher overall xylose yield were 190°C for 6 min and 200 °C for 6 min (13.7 and 13.2 g/100 g dry giant bamboo, respectively, Figure 4B) which equated respectively to 72.9 and 70% of the maximum theoretical. A similar xylose recovery was obtained by Shao et al.¹⁸ for steam pretreatment of bamboo at 210 °C for 5 min.

The total sugar recovery (glucose and xylose) for the different CSF is represented in Figure 5. The pretreatment conditions that provided the maximum sugar recovery (52.4 g sugars/100 g dry giant bamboo, 81.2% of the sugar in raw material) after pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis were 214 °C for 6 min (CSF=2.25). Comparing results using catalysed steam treatment, the maximum overall sugar yield obtained in our study is higher than 60-70% reported for steam treatment with similar severity factor.³⁶ An ethanol yield of 292 L per dry ton of giant bamboo could theoretically be obtained from these conditions considering an ethanol yield of 0.44 g ethanol/g sugars.³⁷ However, the concentration of inhibitors detected in the liquid fraction would decrease the overall ethanol yield in the absence of a detoxification process step, a robust fermentative yeast or controlled fed-batch modes of substrate feeding to minimize the toxic effect. Therefore, considering overall sugar yield and byproducts formation, the central point of the CCD can be considered as a more realistic option should this feedstock be applied in an SSF process using a xylose-utilizing yeast. Under these conditions, the sum of the overall yield of glucose and xylose was 44.3 g per 100 g dry bamboo, corresponding to a 68.7% of the theoretical yield (Figure 5). At these conditions, it is possible to obtain a theoretical yield of 247 L of ethanol per dry ton of giant bamboo.

4. Conclusions

In order to reach the goals and the envisioned future growth of biofuels, it is essential to extend raw material sources to novel dedicated crops. Perennial herbaceous grasses such as bamboo can play an important role in this respect.

This study showed that SO₂-catalyzed steam pretreatment is an efficient method to obtain fermentable sugars from giant bamboo by enzymatic hydrolysis. After pretreatment, the enzymatic conversion from cellulose to glucose increased between 3.5 and 45.5 times, compared to that of untreated bamboo. Pretreatment conditions with combined severity factor values and enzyme dosages greater than 1.72 and 30 FPU/g WIS, respectively, were required to obtain an efficient glucan digestibility and a good overall glucose recovery. The maximum overall sugar yield of 81.2% (52.4 g/100 g dry giant bamboo) was obtained for the pretreatment performed at 214 °C for 6 minutes (CSF=2.25). However, the most effective pretreatment conditions in terms of conversion of glucan to glucose during enzymatic hydrolysis were 210°C for 9 min (CSF=2.26) after impregnation of the fibers with 2.5 % of SO₂ (w/w liquid). On the other hand, the improvement of glucan susceptibility to enzymatic hydrolysis makes difficult to optimize the hemicellulosic sugars recovery. The maximum xylose recovery (13.7- 13.2 g xylose/g raw material) along with a comparative low presence of inhibitors was found at 190°C for 9 min (CSF=1.45) and 200°C for 6 min (CSF=1.62). The concentration of inhibitory compounds detected in the prehydrolysate originated under these conditions was below inhibitory level for *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Thus, considering overall sugar yield and byproducts formation, the material pretreated at the central point of the CCD (200°C for 6 min, CSF=1.62) can be considered as the most appropriate for SSF when using a xylose-utilizing yeast. At these conditions, it is possible to obtain up to 247 L of ethanol per dry ton of giant bamboo considering hexose and pentose sugars fermentation. This amount could be increased up to 292 L of ethanol per dry ton of giant bamboo with the maximum sugars yield obtained (214 °C for 6 minutes,

CSF=2.25) if the microorganism possesses robust fermentative characteristics as well as a high resistance to pretreatment by-products.

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Tables

Table 1. Variables and corresponding coded levels used in the central composite design.

Variables	Coded Levels				
	-1.4142	-1	0	1	1.4142
Time (min)	1.8	3	6	9	10.2
Temperature (°C)	186	190	200	210	214

Table 2. Chemical composition of giant bamboo *Bambusa balcooa*. Data represents the mean values and standard deviations of six determinations.

Composition		Dry matter (% w/w)
Extractives	Water	5.1 ± 0.4
		(0.6 ± 0.2)
	Ethanol	1.9 ± 0.2
Acetic acid		3.7 ± 0.3
Polysaccharides	Glucan	41.0 ± 2.1
	Xylan	16.7 ± 2.0
	Arabinan	3.1 ± 0.2
Lignin	Acid soluble	9.9 ± 0.2
	Acid insoluble	20.8 ± 0.9
Ash		2.4 ± 0.3
Total		104.6

* Values in brackets indicate the glucose content in the water extractives

Table 3. Combined severity factor (CSF), solid recovery (%), composition of liquid fraction or prehydrolyzate and water insoluble solids (WIS) and enzymatic hydrolysis yield (%) at different enzymes dosages resulting from SO₂ steam explosion pretreatment of giant bamboo (*Bambusa balcooa*).

Pretreatment conditions				Insoluble solids recovery (%)	WIS Fraction % dw			Prehydrolysate yield				EH Yield (%)		
					Carbohydrates % dw (g/ 100 g raw material)		Acid Insoluble Lignin (AIL)	Sugars g/L (g/ 100 g raw material)			Acid Insoluble Lignin (ASL, % dw)			
Run	Temp (°C)	Time (min)	CSF		Glucose	Xylose		Glucose	Xylose	Arabinose		15 FPU/g WIS	30 FPU/g WIS	45 FPU/g WIS
4	190	3	0.53	89.0	51.3 (45.6)	11.3 (10.1)	23.9	7.0 (1.5)	25.1 (4.9)	1.7 (0.3)	6.5	6.9	8.9	13.2
3	210	3	1.72	72.0	60.2 (43.3)	0.6 (0.4)	26.5	7.0 (1.9)	38.3 (11.0)	1.3 (0.3)	4.1	51.2	52.4	72.3
6	190	9	1.45	79.7	57.0 (45.4)	5.7 (4.5)	25.1	7.3 (1.8)	32.8 (12.3)	1.4 (0.4)	4.7	20.6	25.7	42.0
2	210	9	2.26	64.0	64.6 (41.3)	Nd	27.7	6.7 (2.5)	24.4 (9.6)	0.9 (0.3)	4.1	62.7	64.2	91.3
Start Point Temperature														
11	186	6	0.95	87.0	51.7 (45.0)	9.4 (8.2)	22.8	4.6 (1.4)	15.4 (4.8)	1.3 (0.3)	5.7	7.4	9.9	12.9
8	214	6	2.25	63.2	65.5 (41.4)	Nd	26.6	7.2 (2.5)	28.4 (10.1)	1.1 (0.3)	4.4	61.5	75.3	83.8
Start Point Time														
9	200	1.8	1.02	84.4	54.9 (46.3)	11.1 (9.3)	24.9	4.7 (1.5)	22.6 (7.2)	1.5 (0.5)	6.0	8.5	8.7	10.2
10	200	10.2	1.95	72.0	59.7 (43.0)	1.7 (1.2)	23.7	4.4 (1.5)	27.5 (9.7)	0.9 (0.2)	4.4	51.0	61.4	79.8
Central Point														
1	200	6	1.57	71.6	56.8 (40.6)	2.4 (1.7)	26.3	6.8 (2.5)	31.3 (12.8)	1.4 (0.5)	4.7	46.4	47.4	68.3
5	200	6	1.72	72.1	58.2 (41.9)	1.5 (1.1)	26.4	7.0 (1.8)	36.3 (10.4)	1.5 (0.3)	4.3	46.6	51.6	70.8
7	200	6	1.66	78.4	56.5 (44.3)	1.6 (1.2)	25.8	5.4 (1.8)	31.2 (11.5)	1.3 (0.4)	5.1	45.2	54.4	64.5
12	200	6	1.55	77.1	54.7 (42.2)	3.1 (2.4)	27.8	4.8 (1.7)	29.7 (11.1)	1.3 (0.4)	5.0	37.5	50.9	62.4
Average ±standard deviation			1.62±0.08	74.8±3.5	56.5±1.3 (42.3)	2.2±0.7 (1.6)	26.6±0.9	6.0±1.1 (2.0)	32.1±2.9 (11.5)	1.4±0.1 (1.0)	4.8±0.6	43.9±4.3	51.1±2.9	66.5±3.8

Data in brackets represents are expressed as a percentage based on dry weight of raw material; nd: not detected

Figures

Figure 1- Estimated response surface for xylose solubilization in the liquid fraction (g/100g of the raw material) showing the influence of temperature and time at a SO₂ loading of 2.5 % w/w liquid).

Figure 2. Yield of byproducts (acetic acid, furfural and hydroxymethyl furfural (HMF) on the liquid fraction, expressed as g/100 g raw material, as a function of the CSF at different pretreatment conditions.

Figure 3. (A) Standardized Pareto chart for EH yield (%) to study the effects of (A.1.) temperature and time at a fixed enzyme loading of 15 FPU/g WIS and (A.2.) CSF (0.53–2.26) and enzyme loading (15–45 FPU/g WIS). Standardized effects are calculated by dividing the effect by its standard error. (B) Estimated response surface for EH yield showing the influence of (B.1.) temperature and time at a fixed enzyme loading of 15 FPU/g WIS and (B.2.) the CSF (0.53–2.26) and the enzyme dosage (15–45 FPU/g WIS).

Figure 4. Overall yield (g/100 g of raw material) of (A) glucose and (B) xylose after pretreatment (as monomers and oligomers separately) and EH at 45 FPU/g WIS as a function of CSF.

Figure 5. Overall sugar (glucose and xylose) yield (g/100 g of raw material) as a function of the CSF. (■) glucose, (■) xylose, (—) maximum theoretical.